

Note on a Routine Gas Analysis Apparatus.

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The accurate and rapid analysis of gases where methane and hydrogen occur simultaneously, has been the subject of numerous contributions. For ordinary routine analysis, the explosion method is usually followed, but the composition of the explosive mixture, the shape of the explosion vessel, etc., play an important part in diminishing the accuracy of this method. Besides, methane is at times incompletely burnt, and any nitrogen that may be present is converted partially into nitrogen peroxide. The fractional combustion method is unquestionably superior, and, in fact, the most rational procedure for the estimation of a methane-hydrogen, or methane-hydrogen-carbon monoxide mixture.

The present communication arose out of an attempt to construct a gas analysis apparatus for class and research purposes, which could be depended upon, and which could be completed in a comparatively shorter time. Besides, it is extremely desirable that such an apparatus should be capable of being assembled in course of a few hours, and should be such that small volumes of gases of the order of 0.5 to 3 c.c. can be accurately analysed. It should be clearly stated in this connection that excepting the introduction of a vacuum creating system by a long tube (V), with a carefully graduated top, there is no substantially novel feature of the apparatus. This tube (V) which is provided with a good three-way stopper, capable of resisting good vacuum, serves as a Töpler pump for exhausting the volume of gas remaining in the tube containing the catalyst used for fractional combustion. The catalysts used are the ordinarily known ones, copper oxide, and palladium, but we have tried specially prepared manganese dioxide with satisfactory results.

A gas burette (A) is enclosed in a water-jacket (B) operated by a levelling pear (C). It is an 11 c.c. burette, made out of 10 c.c. and one c.c. pipettes, the latter being so graduated that 0.01 c.c. can be easily read. The two pieces are fused together and a correction for the junction is made by calibrating against a known volume. The burette ends in a three-way capillary stopper (D), to one end of which is fused an 1 mm. bore capillary tube, having two capillary limbs attached through two other three-way capillary

A—gas burette. B—water-jacket. C—levelling pear. D, E, F, G—three-way capillary stopcocks. H—fractional combustion tube. I—bromine absorption apparatus. J and N—levelling pears. L—absorption pipette. M—explosion pipette. K—bent pipette for introducing absorbent liquids.

stop-cocks (E) and (F) as shown in the figure. A fourth three-way capillary stop-cock (G) serves for the connection with the fractional combustion tube (H) and the bromine absorption apparatus (I). The ends of the stop-cocks are connected to different absorption and washing systems. Glass to glass rubber connections can also be used without inaccuracy.

In the apparatus we have been using, the total volume of mercury used is 200 c.c. The copper catalyst tube (H) can be used for at least half a dozen times without regenerating the copper oxide, but the regeneration is easily effected after each experiment by drawing air by means of the pump-like system, VJ, whilst the rest of the system is being washed for the next experiment. The introduction of absorbents takes place by means of suitably bent pipettes (K) which are filled with the required absorbent to be blown carefully into the absorption pipette (L) without introducing air. If by any chance, an air bubble is introduced, it can be expelled by manipulating the levelling tube (N) of the explosion pipette (M). The tube V having a three-way stopper (O) can serve also as a gas burette, if necessary. The introduction of the gas to be analysed may take place through *a*, *b* or *c*. The washing of the system is conveniently done by a 5% sulphuric acid solution sucked through *c* from a Winchester bottle. The following actual results of analyses indicate the degree of concordance attainable by ordinary practice.

TABLE I.

Analysis of city illuminating gas.

	By explosion method	Fractional combustion method (CuO at 320° as catalyst)	
Gas taken	10·8 c.c.	10·5 c.c.	10·3 c.c.
After KOH	10·2	9·95	9·75
After alkaline			
Pyrogallol	9·9	9·65	9·45
After Br ₂ water	9·5	9·3	9·05
After ammon. Cu ₂ Cl ₂	8·6	8·4	8·2
After CuO-combustion		4·2	4·0
For explosion gas taken	4·4	3·0	2·8
Oxygen added	10·8	8·5	8·00
After explosion	8·38	6·65	6·20
After KOH	6·62	4·2	3·90
CO ₂	5·55%	5·23%	5·34%
O ₂	2·78%	2·85%	2·90%
Unsaturated	3·7%	3·33%	3·89%
CO	8·3%	8·57%	8·25%
H ₂	39·8%	40·00%	40·77%
CH ₄	31·85%	32·66%	31·84%
	91·98	92·64	92·09
Nitrogen	8·02	7·36	7·01
	100·00	100·00	100·00

TABLE II.

Analysis of a prepared mixture of Hydrogen and Methane (55:45), with palladium asbestos as catalyst.

Gas taken	3.10 c.c.	3.00 c.c.	0.9 c.c.
Oxygen added	8.10	7.00	8.12
After Pd.combustion	9.95	7.90	3.50
For explosion gas taken	9.6	7.3	3.15
After explosion	5.6	4.4	2.20
After KOH	4.25	3.15	1.83
H ₂	55.6%	56.0%	55.5%
CH ₄	45.10%	45.1%	45.5%
	<u>100.70%</u>	<u>101.1%</u>	<u>101.00</u>

Remarks--It would appear from these experiments that the hydrogen was not completely burnt in the palladium tube, as the contraction after explosion for methane was more than twice that of CO₂ formed. This was due to the fact that the Pd-tube was several times used before. When the tube is fresh, some methane is burnt, producing CO₂ and water. The CO₂ is first removed before proceeding with the explosion.

TABLE III.

Analysis of a prepared mixture of hydrogen and methane (70:30) with coarse copper oxide as catalyst.

H ₂ ...	69.90%	69.82%	70.00%
CH ₄ ...	30.10%	30.18%	30.00%
	<u>100.00</u>	<u>100.00</u>	<u>100.00</u>

Purity of electrolytic hydrogen from high pressure electrolyser — Volumes of hydrogen of the order of 0.78 c.c., 0.535 c.c., 0.64 c.c. as also 5.00 c.c. gave by the ordinary explosion method, contractions showing cent per cent purity. The same gas when passed over CuO-tube at 320°, is completely burnt, causing a rush of mercury to fill up the vacuum thus produced. To get a positive reading, dilution with inert gases is necessary.

TABLE IV

Test of the purity of electrolytic hydrogen from high pressure electrolyser.

Gas taken	...	0.78 c.c.	0.535 c.c.	0.64 c.c.
Air added	...	3.60	2.50	2.56
After explosion		3.20	2.23	2.24
Contraction	...	1.18	0.805	0.96
H ₂	...	100.7%	100.2%	100%

The maintenance of a steady temperature of 310 to 320° is necessary to avoid a partial combustion of methane by the copper oxide method of fractional combustion, otherwise the results became erroneous.

The heating furnace employed to heat up the catalyst tube H, was built of nichrome wire wound round a porcelain tube as usual, embedded in a packing of ignited magnesia. The arrangement of the switch, S, permits of quick heating up of the furnace, by first leading the street current direct through the furnace, and of steady maintenance by leading the current through a by-pass of resistance. By substituting a silica tube for the glass, the higher temperature of 900° for the combustion of methane may also be attained. Such a furnace we have been using for the last three months almost daily for eight hours without any inconvenience. A coal gas analysis can be completed in half an hour by one who has got into the swing of the paths of the stop-cocks, and whose fingers have acquired delicate manipulative skill. It should be mentioned here that four to six passages, depending on the reactivity of the catalyst, are sufficient to complete the selective combustion of hydrogen. This portion of the operation does not occupy more than five minutes. If the CuO-catalyst is finely deposited on asbestos, the combustion of hydrogen begins visibly at 245° and is rapidly complete between 280° and 290°.

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